

Priority Issues of Development of Activities of Small Business and Entrepreneurial Entities

Rafael Ishimbayev¹

¹ PhD, senior teacher, Department of “Accounting and Auditing”, Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology

Abstract:

In our article “Actual issues of development of activities of small businesses and entrepreneurship entities” we will identify the factors affecting the development of activities of small businesses and entrepreneurship entities, analyze their problematic aspects and develop systematic solutions for them, wide range of foreign investment funds for the further expansion of their activities. aspects such as engagement are covered.

Keywords: Small business and entrepreneurship, capital investment, foreign investment, domestic production, raw materials, labor force, financial stability, effective management, export and import.

Introduction. The scale of attracting foreign investment funds to our country and creating a business environment in the regions is increasing year by year. This creates the basis for the rapid development of the economy of our republic. Creating an all-round convenient infrastructure is attractive to foreign and local investors. In the end, this fully guarantees the continuity of production and the return of the invested capital with profit.

In Uzbekistan, it is important to create conditions for entrepreneurs based on the location of the regions and the opportunities for the formation of infrastructure.

In order to reduce unemployment in our country, rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship is defined as one of the priority tasks. Determining regional economies is also relevant in this regard.

Effective work is being done to further increase the establishment of small business entities and develop their activities, and to improve the financial health of business entities that are on the verge of ending their activities. In particular, the production and service sector is developing widely in our

country. The creation of additional jobs due to the development of these industries in our republic is gaining importance.

The constant attention of our government to the issue of ensuring the employment of the population and increasing their income creates an opportunity to improve the lifestyle of the population year after year. In order to implement the above goals, government decisions, presidential decrees and decisions aimed at the development of entrepreneurship are adopted every year in our republic.

An example of this is the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 7, 2018 No.3777 on the implementation of the program "Every family is an entrepreneur".

Literature analysis. Research on the topic is relevant today, and scientific research is being conducted. Scientific studies of A.A.Karimov, M.Q.Pardayev, A.Kh.Pardayev, A.Z.Avlokhulov, O.O.Sobirov and others among the economists of our country are of great importance in this regard. The scientific researches of these authors are of great scientific and practical importance, and are of scientific and practical importance in aspects such as the organization of economic entities in our republic, the effective organization and management of their management accounts, the analysis of product production processes, and the increase of population incomes. .

Materials and methods. Today's research aims to find systematic solutions to the problems that are waiting to be solved in the fields. For this, it is necessary to use effective research methods. In particular: observation, generalization, grouping, comparative analysis, conducting a survey, expert evaluation of results, economic analysis and economic-statistical methods are effective in conducting research.

Analyzes and results. The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2026" defines the tasks of developing the activities of business entities and creating additional jobs as a result.

In this regard, attracting foreign investment funds to our country is gaining priority. Foreign investment funds are relatively more invested in the production and service sector, which means that these sectors are more attractive for investors.

Decisions and decrees adopted in our country are important because they are aimed at supporting small business and private entrepreneurship, which are one of the main links of the economy. Comparative analysis, expert assessment of results, and economic analysis methods were widely used in the effective conduct of scientific research on the issues raised in this article.

Opportunities and conditions created for further improvement of the business environment in the regions, issues of material and technical support are being continuously monitored.

It should be noted that several factors influence the development of small business entities. In recent years, we can see that the number of economic entities has doubled due to the conditions and opportunities created for the establishment of small business entities. But it should be said that not all newly established enterprises are able to organize their activities effectively. In this regard, there are internal and external factors that affect the activity.

First of all - internal factors - we can cite as an example the lack of raw materials for the organization of production, the increase in tax debts, the lack of financial resources for financing production. All these factors are related to problems related to improper organization of management and cost management.

External factors can include price increases as a result of the purchase of raw materials imported from abroad, the emergence of risks that affect various economic and other production activities on a global scale.

In addition, global shortage of resources, various pandemics and their negative consequences are examples of this factor. These factors have a significant impact on the financial situation of enterprises. It can even bring them to the brink of bankruptcy. Therefore, it is important to develop quick measures to eliminate these factors.

Conclusion. In order to develop small business and entrepreneurship, attract foreign investment resources to the sector, and further develop the production and service sector, it is desirable to solve the following issues:

- Correct organization of management based on production activity;
- Cost control in all departments;
- Effective use of existing material and labor resources;
- It is important to solve issues such as increasing investment attractiveness for foreign investors.

Solving the above issues creates an opportunity to finance the activities of small businesses and entrepreneurial entities at the expense of additional resources. Also, the fulfillment of the tasks creates an opportunity to ensure the financial stability of enterprises in the future, to produce relatively cheap and high-quality products, to expand enterprises and to modernize the main funds at the expense of foreign investment funds.

References

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining “2022-2026 yillarga mo‘ljallangan O‘zbekiston Respublikasini rivojlantirish bo‘yicha Taraqqiyot strategiyasi to‘g‘risida”gi Farmoni. 2021 yil.
2. Sobirov O. O. Product Development Cost Factors Affecting Reduction //AMERICAN Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 07.
3. Собиров О. О. Бошқарув ҳисобининг моҳияти ва уни ташкил этишда харажатларнинг ўрни //Scientific Journal of “International Finance& Accounting”.–Т.: ТМИ. – 2022.
4. Собиров О. Молиявий ҳисоботларни халқаро стандартлар талаблари даражасида такомиллаштириш.« //Халқаро молия ва ҳисоб» илмий журнали. – 2021. – Т. 3. – С. 2181-1016.
5. Собиров О. Кичик бизнес ва хусусий тадбиркорликда бухгалтерия ҳисоби ва ҳисоботларини халқаро стандартлар асосида такомиллаштириш //Монография. Наманган. – 2022.
6. Собиров О. Хўжалик юритувчи субъектларда бошқарув ҳисобини самарали юритишни такомиллаштириш //Архив научных исследований. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1.
7. Sobirov O. O. Improment of management accounting methodology in economic entities //Scientific Journal of “International Finance & Accounting” ТМИ. – 2023. – Т. 2. – С. 2181-1016.
8. Sobirov O. O. Improvement of management accounting in economic entities //Abstract of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) Dissertation on Economic Sciences. Tashkent. ТМИ. – 2022.
9. Sobirov O. Boshqaruv hisobida mas’ uliyat markazlarini tashkil etish masalalari. – 2024. Yashil Iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” ilmiy jurnali. 2 (2), 1-9. Yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz. TDIU. Toshkent.
10. Sobirov O. BOSHQARUV HISOBI METODOLOGIYASINI ZAMONAVIY TIZIMLAR ORQALI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING O ‘ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI //Iqtisodiyot va ta’lim. –2024. –Т. 25. –№. 2. –С.60-64.

11. Собиров О. О. Бошқарув ҳисобининг моҳияти ва уни ташкил этишда харажатларнинг ўрни //Scientific Journal of “Internatsional Finance & Accounting”-ТМИ. Тошкент. – 2022. – С. 2181-1016.